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CARPOS

Coachable Robot for Fruit
Picking Operations

D5-Controller for unintentional and intentional pHRI during the coaching and autonomous operation

Abstract:

The purpose of the present deliverable is to report on the control schemes developed for ensuring safety in case of unintentional collision of the robot with the human, as well as the control schemes developed for addressing the intentional physical human-robot interaction during the kinesthetic inspection and correction phase. The former controller is composed of an admittance controller which smoothly decelerates the execution of the task in case of collision with an unexpected obstacle, e.g. a human, and provides compliance properties to the robotic system, in order to ensure the minimization of the energy transferred from the robot to the human, by taking the whole kinematic chain into account (platform & robotics arm). The latter control scheme is designed to render a non-homogeneous impedance, in order to facilitate corrections along the axes with the highest uncertainty of the current knowledge of the skill, in the context of multimodal Learning by Demonstration (visual and kinesthetic). The developed control method is accepted for presentation in the 34th IEEE International Conference on Robot and Human Interactive Communication (IEEE RO-MAN), which will be held at the Eindhoven University of Technology, Eindhoven, The Netherlands, from August 25th to 29th, 2025, and it will be included in its proceedings. The experimental evaluations of both developed control schemes are conducted using the CARPOS robotic system, i.e. using the UR10e robot on the ClearPath Husky platform, and they are presented in the main body of the text and within the paper attached in the Appendix (which is a part of this Deliverable).

Dissemination Level: **PU**

Περίληψη στα Ελληνικά:

Σκοπός του παρόντος παραδοτέου είναι να παρουσιάσει τα σχήματα ελέγχου που αναπτύχθηκαν για τη διασφάλιση της ασφάλειας σε περίπτωση μη-ηθελημένης σύγκρουσης του ρομπότ με τον άνθρωπο, καθώς και τα συστήματα ελέγχου που αναπτύχθηκαν για την αντιμετώπιση της ηθελημένης φυσικής αλληλεπίδρασης ανθρώπου-ρομπότ κατά τη φάση της κιναισθητικής επιθεώρησης και διόρθωσης. Ο πρώτος ελεγκτής αποτελείται από έναν ελεγκτή ενδοτικότητας (admittance controller), ο οποίος επιβραδύνει ομαλά την εκτέλεση της εργασίας σε περίπτωση σύγκρουσης με ένα μη-αναμενόμενο εμπόδιο, π.χ. έναν άνθρωπο, και προσδίδει στο ρομποτικό σύστημα χαρακτηριστικά υποχωρητικότητας, με σκοπό την ελαχιστοποίηση της ενέργειας που μεταφέρεται από το ρομπότ στον άνθρωπο. Το δεύτερο σύστημα ελέγχου έχει σχεδιαστεί ώστε να προσδίδει στο σύστημα χαρακτηριστικά μη-ομοιογενούς μηχανικής εμπέδησης, προκειμένου να διευκολύνει τις διορθώσεις κατά μήκος των αξόνων με τη μεγαλύτερη αβεβαιότητα στη υπάρχουσα γνώση της εκάστοτε δεξιότητας, στο πλαίσιο της πολυτροπικής μάθησης μέσω επίδειξης (οπτικά και κιναισθητικά). Η μέθοδος ελέγχου που αναπτύχθηκε έχει γίνει αποδεκτή για παρουσίαση στο συνέδριο 34th IEEE International Conference on Robot and Human Interactive Communication (IEEE RO-MAN), το οποίο θα πραγματοποιηθεί στο Τεχνολογικό Πανεπιστήμιο του Αϊντχόφεν, στο Αϊντχόφεν της Ολλανδίας, από τις 25 έως τις 29 Αυγούστου 2025, και θα συμπεριληφθεί στα πρακτικά του συνεδρίου. Οι πειραματικές αξιολογήσεις και των δύο συστημάτων ελέγχου διεξήχθησαν στο ρομποτικό σύστημα του έργου CARPOS, δηλαδή χρησιμοποιώντας το ρομπότ UR10e πάνω στην πλατφόρμα ClearPath Husky, και παρουσιάζονται στο κύριο μέρος του παρόντος κειμένου, όπως και στο άρθρο που επισυνάπτεται στο Παράρτημα (αποτελεί μέρος του παραδοτέου).

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1. INTRODUCTION

Robots have been utilized for more than four decades in industrial setups worldwide in large numbers. However, even now, they operate within isolated, by humans, spaces, surrounded by fences and under prevention mechanisms, in order to ensure that they will not take any actions when a human is in their vicinity. As they constitute an important part of industrial production, engineers have set standards regarding their operation close to humans, such as the IEEE 7007-2021, which sets an ontological standard for ethical driven robotics and automation systems, or the ISO/TS 15066: 2016 standard that sets limits to the maximum allowable forces (e.g. 300N for upper arm and elbow joint and 220N for abdomen)¹ and energy transfer to a human body from a robot during a possible collision (e.g. 1.5J for upper arm and elbow joint and 2.4J for abdomen)². The need to ensure the safety of humans becomes even more evident in cases in which robots operate within spaces that humans co-exist or possibly operate, e.g. within farms.

Figure 1 - The two steps of CARPOS learning framework

CARPOS project's aim is to develop a robotic system able to learn from human activity and ultimately (after enough knowledge is accumulated) to perform harvesting tasks autonomously. This means that human-robot co-existence is imperative. In particular, the project's concept solution involves a two-step learning procedure, as shown in Figure 1. The first step involves the visual observation of human activity by the robot, which may in turn involve a number of iterations/demonstrations performed by humans, while having the robot observing the motion.

¹ Vitolo, F.; Rega, A.; Di Marino, C.; Pasquariello, A.; Zanella, A.; Patalano, S. Mobile Robots and Cobots Integration: A Preliminary Design of a Mechatronic Interface by Using MBSE Approach. *Appl. Sci.* 2022, 12, 419. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12010419>

² Mhenni, F.; Vitolo, F.; Rega, A.; Plateaux, R.; Hehenberger, P.; Patalano, S.; Choley, J.-Y. Heterogeneous Models Integration for Safety Critical Mechatronic Systems and Related Digital Twin Definition: Application to a Collaborative Workplace for Aircraft Assembly. *Appl. Sci.* 2022, 12, 2787. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12062787>

The second step, however, involves the physical interaction of the human-teacher with the robot. In fact, in this step, the robot attempts to execute the task, as observed and learned from the first step, while the human-teacher can intervene by applying corrective forces to the motion in order to kinesthetically correct it. To facilitate the human kinesthetic corrections, this step exploits the estimated uncertainty from the “visual” phase, to allow larger corrections along the corresponding directions, during this “intentional” physical interaction. Due to these system requirements, the control schemes developed in CARPOS project for tackling physical human-robot interaction are divided into two categories:

- The control schemes for ensuring the safety of the human during the unintentional collision with the human.
- The control schemes for facilitating the kinesthetic corrections of the learned skill, based on the estimated uncertainty of the current knowledge.

1.1 Structure of the Deliverable and relation to other deliverables

The proposed method for tackling the problem of unintentional physical human-robot interaction, i.e. in case of unexpected collision, is detailed in Section 2 of the deliverable including its experimental evaluation. On the other hand, the developed control scheme for facilitating the kinesthetic corrections in the second step of the learning procedure is briefly explained in Section 3, as it is detailed in the paper attached in Appendix (end of this document), which includes its experimental validation and evaluation.

The methods developed in this deliverable are integrated within the overall CARPOS system in two different operational phases of the system. The first one is during the autonomous execution of the fruit picking procedure, i.e., when the system has already learned the skill, in which an unintentional collision of the robot with the human is possible, while the other one is during the learning procedure, where the human intentionally physically guides the robot for demonstrating possible corrections. In this way, the work carried out in this deliverable is closely related to the work performed and detailed in “D8 – System integration and Testing”. Furthermore, the work is also related to “D6 – Graphical human-machine interface and skill extraction through proprioceptive data”, as in the whole system integration, the overall kinesthetic correction phase is initiated by the human-user through the graphical interface, while the corrections are related to the proprioceptive data provided to the system by the robot during the kinesthetic guidance. Moreover, as the method for facilitating the user towards the directions of the highest uncertainty is based on the estimated uncertainty of the visual observation, this deliverable is also related to “D4- Control schemes for occlusion-free active perception”, in which the uncertainty of the visual observation plays a significant role.

2. CONTROL SCHEME FOR UNINTENTIONAL COLLISION DURING AUTONOMOUS OPERATION

The complete motion for reaching the fruit during the **autonomous harvesting** procedure performed by the robot (this is the part of the motion in which an unexpected collision with a human can possibly occur), can be divided into the following three sub-phases:

1. **The fruit is detected** based on the visual information provided by the RGB-D camera's of the robot. In this phase at least one fruit is considered to be within the field-of-view of the in-hand camera of the robot. The outcome of this phase is the pose of the first fruit detected. Let $\{F\}$ be the frame of the fruit and $\{C\}$ the frame of the in-hand camera (all the frames are depicted in Fig. 2) as detected by the system. Further, let $\mathbf{p}_{cf} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{R}_{cf} \in SO(3)$ be its pose (i.e. position and orientation), in the form of Cartesian coordinates and rotation matrix respectively with respect to $\{C\}$. The detection of the fruit and the extraction of its coordinate frame is detailed in "D3 – Fruit Picking Action Identification and Skill Extraction from Visual Observation", which is related to the perceptual algorithms employed towards this direction.
2. **The grasp and pre-grasp poses for the robotic hand are then calculated**, based on the grasping pose taught to the system through the visual observation of the skill during the human demonstration, with the pre-grasp pose having a predefined offset in translation with respect to the frame of the robotic hand. Let $\{G\}$ and $\{Pr\}$ be the grasp and pre-grasp coordinate frames, with $\mathbf{p}_{0g} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{R}_{0g} \in SO(3)$ and $\mathbf{p}_{0pr} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{R}_{0pr} \in SO(3)$ be the poses (in the form of Cartesian coordinates and rotation matrix) of them respectively, with respect to the inertial frame $\{0\}$ (we consider the initial pose of the robotic platform as the inertial frame). To calculate these poses, we utilize the following formulas, which are based on simple consecutive multiplications of homogeneous transformations:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_{0g} & \mathbf{p}_{0g} \\ \mathbf{0}_{1 \times 3} & 1 \end{bmatrix} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_{0c} & \mathbf{p}_{0c} \\ \mathbf{0}_{1 \times 3} & 1 \end{bmatrix}}_{\text{Forward kinematics of the in-hand camera}} \cdot \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_{cf} & \mathbf{p}_{cf} \\ \mathbf{0}_{1 \times 3} & 1 \end{bmatrix}}_{\text{Fruit detection}} \cdot \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_{fg} & \mathbf{p}_{fg} \\ \mathbf{0}_{1 \times 3} & 1 \end{bmatrix}}_{\text{Captured from human demonstration}}, \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_{0pr} & \mathbf{p}_{0pr} \\ \mathbf{0}_{1 \times 3} & 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_{0c} & \mathbf{p}_{0c} \\ \mathbf{0}_{1 \times 3} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_{cf} & \mathbf{p}_{cf} \\ \mathbf{0}_{1 \times 3} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_{fg} & \mathbf{p}_{fg} + \mathbf{p}_{pof} \\ \mathbf{0}_{1 \times 3} & 1 \end{bmatrix},$$

where $\mathbf{p}_{pof} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the predefined offset for the pre-grasp pose (e.g., $[0.1 \ 0 \ 0]^T m$) with respect to the fruit's frame, $\mathbf{p}_{0c} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{R}_{0c} \in SO(3)$ the pose of the in-hand camera with respect to frame $\{0\}$ and $\mathbf{p}_{fg} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{R}_{fg} \in SO(3)$ the learned pose of the human hand with respect to the frame of the fruit, as captured from the visually perceived human demonstration. More details can be found in "D3 – Fruit Picking Action Identification and Skill Extraction from Visual Observation".

Figure 2 - Considered frames for the autonomous execution and kinesthetic corrections

3. Lastly, **the end-effector is performing a sequence of two motions**, using the complete kinematic chain (robotic platform and manipulator): from its initial pose, denoted with $\mathbf{p}_{0i} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{R}_{0i} \in SO(3)$, to the calculated pre-grasp pose, i.e. $\mathbf{p}_{0pr} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{R}_{0pr} \in SO(3)$, and in turn to the grasp pose, i.e. $\mathbf{p}_{0g} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{R}_{0g} \in SO(3)$. To achieve this, a smooth 5th order minimum-jerk trajectory is generated as a reference for the end-effector of the robot, which is linear in translation and follows the minimum geodesic distance in orientation (i.e. the minimum angle of rotation). Let this trajectory be $\mathbf{p}_d(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{R}_d(t) \in SO(3)$, with $\dot{\mathbf{p}}_d(t)$, $\boldsymbol{\omega}_d \in \mathbb{R}^3$ being the corresponding linear and angular reference velocity and $\ddot{\mathbf{p}}_d(t)$, $\dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_d(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ the corresponding linear and angular reference acceleration. In order to provide the system with compliant properties and therefore ensure the safety of the human during a possible unintentional collision, we employ the notion of admittance control, and we combine it with a phase-stopping mechanism that essentially halts the motion generation, when an unexpected collision is detected, in order to prevent the system from inducing further forces to the human. The developed control scheme towards this direction is detailed in the next sub-section.

2.1 ADMITTANCE CONTROL WITH PHASE-STOPPING

For the motion of the end-effector we consider the whole kinematic chain as a complete mechanism, as shown in Figure 3. This means that to actuate the end-effector we consider the motion of all 8 joints simultaneously, making the whole robotic mechanism redundant for following a specific pose with its end-effector, as only six degrees of freedom are required for such a motion. In particular, the employed robotic platform, namely ClearPath Husky, belongs to the category of the “differential-drive” wheeled platforms, which means that it can only execute translations along its x -axis and rotations around its z -axis (see Figure 3). Furthermore, the robotic manipulator utilized, which is a UR10e arm, has six rotational joints. Let $\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{R} \in SO(3)$ be the position and orientation of the end-effector (i.e. robotic gripper/hand) respectively with respect to the inertial frame $\{0\}$, which can be analytically found by combining the odometry of the platform (provided by the manufacturer of the platform) and the forward kinematics of

Figure 3 - The whole kinematic chain is considered for the motion of the end-effector

the UR10e robot (e.g. derived using the Robotics Toolbox kit for Python by Peter Corke³). In particular, the pose of the end-effector is calculated by the following relationship:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R} & \mathbf{p} \\ \mathbf{0}_{1 \times 3} & 1 \end{bmatrix} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_{0h} & \mathbf{p}_{0h} \\ \mathbf{0}_{1 \times 3} & 1 \end{bmatrix}}_{\text{Pose of the Husky platform from odometry}} \cdot \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_{hu} & \mathbf{p}_{hu} \\ \mathbf{0}_{1 \times 3} & 1 \end{bmatrix}}_{\text{Constant pose of the UR10e base wrt to the Husky platform}} \cdot \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_{ue} & \mathbf{p}_{ue} \\ \mathbf{0}_{1 \times 3} & 1 \end{bmatrix}}_{\text{Forward kinematics of the UR10e robot}}, \quad (2)$$

The mapping between the velocity of the end-effector and the joint velocities is then provided by the following formula:

$$\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{J}_c(\mathbf{R}_{0h}, q_1, \dots, q_6) \dot{\mathbf{q}}, \quad (3)$$

where

$$\mathbf{q} \triangleq [q_1 \dots q_8]^T \in \mathbb{R}^8 \quad (4)$$

is the vector of the joint variables of the complete kinematic chain (depicted in Figure 3), with $q_1, \dots, q_6 \in \mathbb{R}^6$ being the joint variables of the robotic manipulator, $\dot{q}_7 \triangleq v_x \in \mathbb{R}$ corresponding to the linear velocity of the platform along the x -axis of the platform, $\dot{q}_8 \triangleq \omega_z \in \mathbb{R}$ corresponding to the angular velocity of the platform around the z -axis of the platform (as shown in Figure 3),

$$\mathbf{v} \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\mathbf{p}} \\ \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^6, \quad (5)$$

is the generalized velocity of the end-effector with respect to the inertial frame $\{0\}$ and

$$\mathbf{J}_c(\mathbf{R}_{0h}, q_1, \dots, q_6) \triangleq {}^6\mathbf{R}_{0h} [\mathbf{J}_m(q_1, \dots, q_6) \quad \mathbf{J}_h(q_1, \dots, q_6)] \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 8} \quad (6)$$

is the Jacobian of the complete kinematic chain, with $\mathbf{J}_m(q_1, \dots, q_6) \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 6}$ being the Jacobian of the UR10e robotic manipulator,

$${}^6\mathbf{R}_{0h} \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_{0h} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{R}_{0h} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 6},$$

and

$$\mathbf{J}_h \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} 1 & & & & & \\ 0 & -\mathcal{S}(\mathbf{p}_{he})\mathbf{z} & & & & \\ 0 & & & & & \\ 0 & 0 & & & & \\ 0 & 0 & & & & \\ 0 & 1 & & & & \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 2}, \quad (7)$$

³ <https://github.com/petercorke/robotics-toolbox-python>

being the part of the Jacobian to map the velocity of the platform (i.e. \dot{q}_7, \dot{q}_8) to generalized velocities at the end-effector, $\mathbf{p}_{he}(q_1, \dots, q_6) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ being the position of the end-effector with respect to the platform and $\mathbf{z} \triangleq [0 \ 0 \ 1]^T$.

Given equations (3) and (6), one can solve the inverse kinematics problem in the velocity level to achieve a specific pre-defined generalized velocity with the end-effector. As this specific robotic mechanism is redundant, i.e. it poses more than six degrees of freedom, there are multiple solutions to the inverse kinematics problem. In our case, we employ the weighted pseudo-inverse solution, to balance the distribution of motion between the robotic platform and the manipulator. In this line of thought, the commanded joint velocities, for achieving any arbitrary reference task-space generalized velocity with the end-effector, denoted with \mathbf{v}_r , can be calculated by:

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}_c = \mathbf{J}_c^{w\dagger} \mathbf{v}_r, \quad (8)$$

where $\dot{\mathbf{q}}_c \in \mathbb{R}^8$ are the commanded joint velocities and $\mathbf{J}_c^{w\dagger} \in \mathbb{R}^{8 \times 6}$ the weighted pseudoinverse of $\mathbf{J}_c(\mathbf{p}_{0h}, \mathbf{R}_{0h}, q_1, \dots, q_6)$, which is the following:

$$\mathbf{J}_c^{w\dagger} \triangleq \mathbf{W}^{-1} \mathbf{J}_c^T (\mathbf{J}_c \mathbf{W}^{-1} \mathbf{J}_c^T)^{-1}, \quad (9)$$

with $\mathbf{W} \in S_{++}^6$ (S_{++}^6 denotes the set of positive definite matrices) being a predefined weight matrix, which in our case is selected to be diagonal and equal to:

$$\mathbf{W} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_6 & \mathbf{0}_{6 \times 2} \\ \mathbf{0}_{2 \times 6} & 10^3 \mathbf{I}_2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (10)$$

This specific selection, e.g. (10), allocates the velocity effort mainly to the manipulator, as compared to the robotic platform. The opposite rationale should be utilized in case in which rough motions of the end-effector in task space would be considered, e.g. during navigation, which lies outside the focus of this project.

For providing compliant properties to the robotic system, an admittance controller is employed. We opted for this specific controller, in contrast to its dual implementation, i.e. the impedance controller, as our system accepts velocity commands and not torque commands. Following the admittance controller's principles, we firstly define an impedance model, which in our case is selected to be the following:

$$\mathbf{M} \mathbf{d}_v + \mathbf{D} \mathbf{d}_v + \mathbf{K} \mathbf{d} = \mathbf{F}_x \quad (11)$$

where

$$\mathbf{d} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_r - \mathbf{p}_d \\ \log(\mathbf{R}_r \mathbf{R}_d^T) \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^6 \quad (12)$$

is the desired deviation of the reference pose, i.e. $\mathbf{p}_r \in \mathbb{R}^3, \mathbf{R}_r \in SO(3)$, from the trajectory, i.e. $\mathbf{p}_d \in \mathbb{R}^3, \mathbf{R}_d \in SO(3)$, with $\log(\cdot) : SO(3) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$ the logarithmic mapping of the rotation matrix (i.e. returning the angle-axis azimuth), while

$$\mathbf{d}_v = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\mathbf{p}}_r - \dot{\mathbf{p}}_d \\ \boldsymbol{\omega}_r - \boldsymbol{\omega}_d \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^6 \quad (13)$$

is the desired deviation of the generalized velocity, $\mathbf{M}, \mathbf{D}, \mathbf{K} \in S_{++}^6$ the target inertia, damping and stiffness matrices respectively and $\mathbf{F}_x \in \mathbb{R}^6$ being the external considered force-torque vector, which in our case is provided by the embedded force-torque sensor at the end-effector of the robot. To give a better understanding of the admittance control rationale, given the measured external forces, e.g. in case of an unexpected collision, we want the end-effector to behave as a mass-spring-damper system. Therefore, given the force/torque measurements, i.e. $\mathbf{F}_x \in \mathbb{R}^6$, we integrate online the model, i.e. (11), which provides us with \mathbf{d}_v , from which one can easily derive the desired reference velocity $\mathbf{v}_r \triangleq [\dot{\mathbf{p}}_r \ \boldsymbol{\omega}_r]$, as the desired trajectory is designed by the system as explained above (i.e. using a 5th order polynomial) which in turn is fed to (8) to calculate the real-time joint velocity commands that are provided on-line to the robot (platform and robotic manipulator simultaneously).

One of the main problems in safe but autonomous operation is the balance between accuracy and compliance, as the one objective opposes the other. In particular, high compliance guarantees, in most of the cases, comes with low accuracy in the task, while executing a task with high accuracy guarantees can mean that safety guarantees can be potentially sacrificed. In our case, performance with high accuracy is substantial, to ensure that the exact grasp pose learned from the human demonstrations is reached. If this accuracy is not achieved, this could even result in ineffective grasping of the fruit. To resolve this problem, we employ a thresholding-filter to ensure that the task is performed with high accuracy when no collision has occurred and smoothly switch to full compliance when an unexpected collision is detected. Towards this direction, we utilize the following formula:

$$\mathbf{F}_x \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{f}_x \\ \boldsymbol{\tau}_x \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^6 \quad (14)$$

where $\mathbf{f}_x, \boldsymbol{\tau}_x \in \mathbb{R}^3$ are the force and torques composing \mathbf{F}_x , which are fed to (11), and

$$\mathbf{f}_x = \begin{cases} (\|\mathbf{f}_m\| - f_t) \frac{\mathbf{f}_m}{\|\mathbf{f}_m\|} & , \text{if } \|\mathbf{f}_m\| > f_t \\ \mathbf{0}_3 & , \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_x = \begin{cases} (\|\boldsymbol{\tau}_m\| - \tau_t) \frac{\boldsymbol{\tau}_m}{\|\boldsymbol{\tau}_m\|} & , \text{if } \|\boldsymbol{\tau}_m\| > \tau_t \\ \mathbf{0}_3 & , \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

with $\mathbf{f}_m, \boldsymbol{\tau}_m \in \mathbb{R}^3$ being the measured forces and torques provided by the 6-dof force/torque sensor attached to the wrist of the robot (embedded) and $f_t, \tau_t \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ being the predefined force and torque thresholds. The employed function, for a scalar measurement (for presentation purposes), is shown in Figure 4. Notice that, using this rationale, two zones are determined, namely the “High accuracy zone”, in which the motion of the robot is not affected by the external forces possibly due to unmodelled dynamics of interaction with the rest of the environment, and a “Safety ensuring zone”, which passes the value of the force to the admittance controller, i.e. (11), thereby inducing a compliant motion for the robot.

Figure 4 - Thresholding function used for balancing safety and accuracy

Although the employment of compliant control methods, such as the admittance controller used here, is already deemed to provide safety guarantees in the event of a possible collision with a human, one crucial aspect during physical human-robot interaction is to ensure that the robot will not proceed in executing the task further, i.e. generating further reference trajectory after the collision, as demonstrated in Figure 5, as this could yield sufficient forces to damage the human, due to the stiffness term of the model, i.e. (11).

Figure 5 - The importance of phase-stopping

In CARPOS we employed the concept of “phase-stopping” for the trajectory generation mechanism by considering a virtual time $t_v \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$, that replaces the time variable in the trajectory generation mechanism. The condition for stopping this “virtual time” variable is provided as given below:

$$\dot{t}_v \triangleq \frac{dt_v}{dt} = \begin{cases} 1 & , \text{if } \|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_d(t_v)\| < e_t \\ 0 & , \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

where $e_t \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ a pre-defined threshold for the deviation between the actual end-effector and the trajectory generated. Notice that $\|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_d(t_v)\|$ could evolve due to external forces and the action of admittance. Following this line of thought, the position and velocity of the generated trajectory is provided by using the 5th order polynomial with respect to t_v , i.e. as given below:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{p}_d(t) &= \mathbf{p}_d(t_v(t)), \\ \dot{\mathbf{p}}_d(t) &\triangleq \frac{d\mathbf{p}_d}{dt} = \frac{d\mathbf{p}_d}{dt_v} \frac{dt_v}{dt}. \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Notice that only the deviation in the position is taken into account, as this part of the motion is considered to be the important part during collision, i.e. in a collision only forces are applied to the end-effector and scarcely torques.

Lastly, to ensure that the force exerted by the user stay in low levels, we replace the stiffness term of (11) with a term derived from the gradient of a “saturated artificial potential”⁴; both the potential and its gradient are depicted in Figure 6. Therefore, (11) becomes:

$$\mathbf{M} \dot{\mathbf{d}}_v + \mathbf{D} \mathbf{d}_v + \mathbf{F}_k = \mathbf{F}_x, \quad (18)$$

where

$$\mathbf{F}_k \triangleq \frac{\partial V(\mathbf{d})}{\partial \mathbf{d}} \frac{\partial \mathbf{d}(\mathbf{p})}{\partial \mathbf{p}} = \begin{cases} \mathbf{K} \mathbf{d} & , \text{if } \|\mathbf{K} \mathbf{d}\| < f_{kth} \\ \frac{f_{kth} \mathbf{K} \mathbf{d}}{\|\mathbf{K} \mathbf{d}\|} & , \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

with $f_{kt} \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ being a pre-defined threshold for the force induced by the stiffness term, above which it is saturated, in a continuous manner.

Figure 6 - The saturated artificial potential employed

⁴ Suguru Arimoto. 1996. Control Theory of Nonlinear Mechanical Systems. Oxford University Press, Inc., USA.

2.2 Experimental validation of the controller for unintentional collision

For the experimental evaluation, the CARPOS integrated hardware is utilized, namely the Husky ClearPath robotic platform with a UR10e robotic manipulator. The kinematics of the robot combines the analytic calculations described above, involving the kinematics of the manipulator (i.e. forward kinematics and Jacobian), which are calculated employing the Robotics Toolbox of Peter Corke (link is provided above). The parameter values utilized are $\mathbf{p}_{prof} = [0.1 \ 0 \ 0]^T \text{m}$, $\mathbf{M} = 2\mathbf{I}_3 \text{kg}$, $\mathbf{D} = 10\mathbf{I}_3 \text{Ns/m}$, $\mathbf{K} = 40\mathbf{I}_3 \text{N/m}$, $e_t = 0.1 \text{m}$, $f_t = 30 \text{N}$ and $f_{kth} = 5 \text{N}$. Notice the admittance model is considered only for the position, as this part of the motion constitutes the crucial part for safety.

The experiments are performed in real tomato plants, using a realistic mock-up tomato. For evaluating the system in realistic conditions, we firstly perform the detection of the tomato using the algorithms developed within the project, as shown in Figure 7 and Figure 8. The following two cases, involving different realistic examples of collision, which test different levels of human responses, are considered:

- **[Front - Abdomen]:** In this case, the human has the robot in front of him, as shown in Figure 7. This case considers relatively quicker (as compared to the other case) human responses, as the robot is partially within the human's field of view. The considered scenario involves the collision of the robot, while the human is engaged in a hand-over task with another human. The part of the body which contacts the robot is the abdomen of the human. Let us highlight that the robot was in motion when the collision with the human occurred.
- **[Back - Elbow]:** In this case, the robot is behind the human, therefore it is not within the field of view of the human, as shown in Figure 8. The considered scenario involves the collision of the robot with the back part of the hand (elbow) of the human, while the human performs a process to the tomato plant. The human was not aware of the exact point at which the robot will collide with him. Similarly to the previous case, the robot was in motion when the collision with the human occurred.

Figure 7 - Experiment considering a collision with abdomen

Figure 8- Experiment considering the collision with elbow (robot is not within the human's FoV)

In Figure 9, the paths followed by the end-effector are depicted in both considered cases. Notice the reaction of the trajectory generation mechanism that is able to stop the trajectory generation (black circle, in Figure 9 indicates the instance in which the collision was detected), as well as the compliance of the robot, reflected by the lateral deviation of the actual path (blue line) from the reference one (red dashed line), due to the employed saturated admittance controller and the phase stopping mechanism. Let us note that in the second case (back - elbow) the robot contacted the human twice, possibly due to the slow human responses. Lastly, let us note that the reference evolved no further than 0.01m after the collision, in both cases.

a) Collision with abdomen

b) Collision with elbow (not in the human FOV)

Figure 9- Path of the end-effector in both cases

a) [Abdomen] Force

b) [Abdomen] Energy

c) [Elbow] Force

d) [Elbow] Energy

Figure 10- The norm of the force and the energy in both cases

In Figure 10, the time evolution of the force magnitude and cumulative energy are depicted in both considered cases, during the contact of the human with the robot. For enhancing fairness in the evaluation of the results, we integrate only the power transferred from the robot to the human, without accounting for the energy returned back from the human to the robot (as this would lead to much lower energy due to the opposite sign). In particular, the energy is calculated as follows:

$$E(t) = \int_0^t \max(0, -\dot{\mathbf{p}}^T \mathbf{F}_p) dt,$$

with $\mathbf{F}_p \in \mathbb{R}^3$ being the measured force, i.e. \mathbf{f}_m , during the collision of the human with the robot. Notice the minus sign, which is considered to only account for the energy transferred from the robot to the human, i.e. for the instances in which the force applied to the human is against the velocity of the robot (if only $\dot{\mathbf{p}}^T \mathbf{F}_p$ was considered, then the total energy would be significantly lower, i.e. close to zero).

In terms of the forces, depicted in Figure 10a and c for the two cases respectively, one can easily see that the maximum force exerted by the robot to the human is no more than **38N** and **60N** for the two cases respectively. These values are both lower than the target upper limit set to KPI2.1 defined in “Deliverable 1 –Requirements, use-cases and KPIs of CARPOS”, which is 100N. Furthermore, these values are also much lower than the ones defined in the ISO/TS 15066: 2016 standard that sets the limits of the maximum allowed forces to **220N** for abdomen and **300N** for upper arm and elbow joint respectively.

In terms of the transferred energy, depicted in Figure 10b and d for the two cases respectively, one can easily see that the total energy transferred by the robot to the human are **~0.28J** and **~0.45J** for the two cases respectively, which are much lower than the maximum allowed ones defined in the ISO/TS 15066: 2016 standard that are **2.4J** for abdomen and **1.5J** for upper arm respectively.

3. CONTROL SCHEME FOR FACILITATING COACHING

Here, only a brief overview of the method is provided, as the method is detailed in the attached paper in Appendix A.

The work described in this part of the Deliverable is for enabling the kinesthetic inspection and correction of the learned skill, considering that initially a visual observation (or multiple ones) are performed and the skill is already learned with some uncertainty. The necessity of such a second step (that of inspection and kinesthetic correction) sources from the limitations of the visual sensors, as in most cases, the depth estimation comes with high uncertainty, as presented in Figure 11.

Based on the above, here we develop a controller which allows the human-user to inspect the already known skill, optically and haptically (through contact forces), while making him able of intervening in any time by applying forces for correcting the skill. In particular, for facilitating the coaching of the skill, we developed a method that combines the advantages of both visual and kinesthetic teaching, offering the intuitiveness and effortlessness of learning through observation while benefiting from the accuracy of kinesthetic teaching. The proposed method assumes access to an algorithm for detecting the human-hand configuration from RGB images (without depth or camera distance information), and does not require knowledge of the camera's location relative to an inertial frame.

Figure 11 - Considered uncertainty of the visual observation

Let the motion captured by the camera be encoded using a Dynamic Movement Primitives model (more details about the encoding of the skill can be found in Deliverable 7 – “Multimodal skill encoding and generalization in fruit geometry variations”) of the following form:

$$\tau \dot{\mathbf{x}}_d = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_d; \mathbf{W}), \quad (20)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_d \triangleq [\mathbf{p}_d^T \ \mathbf{Q}_d^T \ \dot{\mathbf{p}}_d^T \ \boldsymbol{\omega}_d^T \ z]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{14}$ is the state of the model (motion generation mechanism), with $\mathbf{p}_d \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{Q}_d \in \mathbb{S}^3$ being the generated reference position and unit quaternion respectively, $\boldsymbol{\omega}_d \in \mathbb{R}^3$ the generated angular velocity reference, and $z \in \mathbb{R}$ the so-called phase variable that serves as a replacement of time (one can refer to [5] for more details). Moreover, $\mathbf{f}(\cdot): \mathbb{R}^{14} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{14}$

⁵ A. J. Ijspeert, J. Nakanishi, H. Hoffmann, P. Pastor, and S. Schaal, “Dynamical movement primitives: Learning attractor models for motor behaviors,” *Neural Comput.*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 328–373, Feb 2013.

is the nonlinear function that maps the states to their derivatives, $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times N}$ the tunable parameters that essentially encode the motion, with $N \in \mathbb{N}$ being their number, while $\tau \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ is the time scaling parameter, through which the speed and duration of motion can be adjusted; $\tau > 1$ induces a motion with lower speed than the one demonstrated, while $\tau < 1$ induces a faster motion. Given the demonstrated motion, there are many different options to compute the \mathbf{W} values so that the generated motion (i.e. the evolution of the dynamical system) optimally mimics the demonstrated data set. The most common methods for calculating the optimal parameters \mathbf{W} are the Least Squares and the Locally Weighted Regression [5].

To provide the system with compliant characteristics, we employ the notion of admittance control, similarly to the one detailed in the previous section of this Deliverable, i.e. this provided in equation (11). Therefore, a target impedance model in the task-space of the robot is defined for the robot's end-effector.

The estimated hand pose by the camera includes a measurement error, which is considered to be a random variable having a normal distribution: $\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}_6, \boldsymbol{\Sigma})$, with $\boldsymbol{\Sigma} \in S_{++}^6$ being the variance-covariance matrix of its uncertainty with respect to the inertial frame. In practical applications, as $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$ is generally unknown, one can use an estimate of the uncertainty. More specifically, given the initial robot's end-effector pose at the start of the kinesthetic correction phase, denoted as $\mathbf{R}_0 \in SO(3)$, the uncertainty with respect to the robot's base frame is calculated as follows:

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma} \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_p & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_o \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{A} \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_c \mathbf{A}^\top, \quad (21)$$

where $\mathbf{A} \triangleq \mathbf{R}_0 \mathbf{R}_{cu}^\top \otimes \mathbf{I}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^6$ with $\mathbf{R}_{cu} \in SO(3)$ being the rotation matrix of initially identified pose of the human hand with respect to the camera frame and " \otimes " representing the Kronecker product, while $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_c \in S_{++}^6$ represents the block-diagonal (for decoupled position and orientation) uncertainty of the camera with respect to its own frame. In such a case, for an RGB camera (or for a low-depth-resolution RGB-D camera), we could consider $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_c = \text{diag}(\underline{\sigma}, \underline{\sigma}, \bar{\sigma}, \underline{\zeta}, \bar{\zeta}, \underline{\zeta})^2$ with $\underline{\sigma}, \bar{\sigma}, \underline{\zeta}, \bar{\zeta} \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ and $\underline{\sigma} \ll \bar{\sigma}, \underline{\zeta} \ll \bar{\zeta}$, as the estimation involves low uncertainty only along the pixel space direction (x, y of the camera) and the rotation around its z -axis (see Figure 11). Notice that the units of $\underline{\sigma}, \bar{\sigma}$ are "meters" and those of $\underline{\zeta}, \bar{\zeta}$ are "radians". Hence, the expected deviations can be estimated on the basis of rough estimates for the motion's range. Under the aforementioned rationale, and given the uncertainty involved in the DMP model after the initial stage (i.e. visual training), we propose the utilization of the following anisotropic stiffness matrix:

$$\mathbf{K} \triangleq \text{diag} \left(\frac{k_p}{\lambda_{pM}} \mathbf{I}_3, \frac{k_o}{\lambda_{oM}} \mathbf{I}_3 \right) \boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{-1}, \quad (22)$$

where $\lambda_{pM}, \lambda_{oM} \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ respectively denote the maximum eigenvalues of $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_p^{-1}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_o^{-1}$, while $k_p, k_o \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ represent the selected stiffness value on the major axis of \mathbf{K} for position and orientation, respectively.

More details about the method can be found in the full paper available in Appendix A.

2.2 Experimental validation of the controller for inspection and kinesthetic correction

The proposed scheme of multi-modal LbD was experimentally evaluated considering the scenario shown in Figure 12. The task involves moving a tool along a circular path (approximately 1.5 turns) around an axis, to which the tool is connected via a thread. A plain RGB webcam (Creative Live! Cam) is used to capture data for visual training, in 30 fps. The image captured by the camera is shown in Figure 13. Note that, given the viewpoint of the camera, the motion trajectory is ellipsoidal when projected to the camera's visual plane. The robotic agent is a Universal Robots UR10e manipulator, equipped with a custom gripper. A custom dual-handle attachment developed in the CARPOS project is utilized, mounted between the robot's tool flange and the gripper, which facilitates hand guidance of the robot during kinesthetic training. A pushbutton, integrated in one of the handles, is used to allow user intervention by engaging the kinesthetic correction mode during execution of the visually learned motion.

Figure 12-The post-grasp task considered for the experimental evaluation of the proposed method.

Figure 13 - Snapshots of the visual teaching stage, acquired by the webcam during the task demonstration.

The paths of the robot's tip followed during the proposed kinesthetic corrections method (blue line) and during single-modal kinesthetic-only teaching (red line) are shown in Figure 14a, alongside with the visually trained model (black line). It can be observed that due to the lack of depth information in the RGB video, the visually trained motion remains essentially planar and takes on an ellipsoidal shape. The trajectory of the kinesthetic-only training exhibits considerable oscillations, resulting from the fact that the human experiences the dynamics of the system. It should also be noted that, in this case, the user was unable to complete the demonstration within the nominal task duration of 10.5 s, with the motion ending approximately a quarter-circle early. This reflects the high cognitive load imposed on the user while attempting to compensate for the robot's dynamics.

Figure 14 - Path followed by the robot's tip during (a) training, and (b) execution of the learned task. Black dashed line depicts a circle of radius equal to the thread's length (0.225m), while the solid small linear segments indicate the tool z-axis at regular time intervals. The initial and final positions are denoted with "x" and "o" markers respectively (all initial positions coincide).

A detailed evaluation of the results, involving the effort of the human and a quantitative analysis of the performance of the method can be found in the published paper provided in Appendix A of this deliverable.

APPENDIX – PREPRINT VERSION OF THE ACCEPTED PAPER

Dimitrios Papageorgiou, Charalampos Athanasiadis, John Fasoulas and Michael Sfakiotakis, "Towards multi-modal Learning by Demonstration: Combining depthless visual data with kinesthetic teaching", Accepted at the 34th IEEE International Conference on Robot and Human Interactive Communication (IEEE RO-MAN), Eindhoven, The Netherlands.

Towards multi-modal Learning by Demonstration: Combining depthless visual data with kinesthetic teaching

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Abstract— Human-human learning is usually conducted utilizing multiple modalities (verbal, visual, kinesthetic etc), which is proven to significantly improve the quality of communication between the teacher and the learner. Towards extending this idea to human-robot learning, we propose here a multi-modal scheme for robot Learning by Demonstration (LbD), that combines visual observation of the human hand from a depthless RGB camera, with enhanced direct kinesthetic teaching of the robot. The proposed method, exploits the visually perceived action of the human hand, to provide haptic guidance during kinesthetic teaching, facilitating corrections along the axes with the maximum uncertainty. The method is experimentally evaluated using an RGB camera and a UR10e robot, and compared against single-modal approaches, i.e. visually trained behavior and trained through kinesthetic teaching. Our method is shown to outperform the latter, in terms of both the quality of skill transfer, and the cognitive/physical load required for the training.

I. INTRODUCTION

Future robots are expected to coexist, collaborate and progressively learn from humans, while alleviating their cognitive and physical burden. Therefore, a key requirement for such systems is the ability to acquire knowledge from humans to develop new skills. Unlike explicit robot programming, which demands technical programming skills, Learning by Demonstration (LbD), or “Programming by Demonstration”, is a notion recently introduced in robotics to provide robots with such capabilities [1], [2].

Learning by Demonstration is based on data from human demonstrations, which can be captured through multiple means. The most dominant methods for capturing such data in the literature either involve external sensors, e.g. cameras or wearable sensors, or employ the notion of “kinesthetic teaching”, according to which the robot is taught through direct physical guidance by the human. Although LbD through visual observation is more intuitive for the human-teacher, it suffers from high uncertainty, sourcing from the sensor characteristics, the detectability of the human hand, and

possible occlusions. On the other hand, data gathered through kinesthetic teaching do not usually involve uncertainty, but the process can be physically and cognitively demanding, due to the robot’s dynamics and the compliant control scheme employed for enabling the physical guidance.

Learning through visual observations of the human-teacher, e.g. visual data captured through a camera, is a well-studied topic in the literature [2]–[10]. Some works tackle the problem in a higher decision-making level [8], considering the prior knowledge of some action-motion primitives (e.g. pushing, pulling), others infer/reconstruct the motion from static RGB images [3], while others consider the problem of capturing and encoding the trajectory of the actual motion required for the task execution from video streams [6], [7], [9], [10]. In the latter category, which is the focus of this paper, some works employ Neural Networks [7], [9], which however require a large-size dataset, e.g. in [9] more than 10,000 videos were utilized to encode the skills, while others utilize a relatively small dataset (max 2-3 videos), e.g. by considering multiple demonstration-iterations while optimizing the view-angle of the observation [6] or by recreating the lost data based on known kinematic models [10]. However, it is commonly accepted in the literature, that data captured through RGB (or even RGB-D) sensors suffer from high uncertainty in the depth axis of the sensor, which heavily affects the quality of LbD.

Kinesthetic teaching enables direct skill transfer by allowing the human to physically guide the robot in demonstrating the motion. In contrast to visual observation, kinesthetic teaching does not involve any uncertainty, as proprioceptive sensors (e.g. joint encoders) of the robot are utilized for capturing the motion. However, since there is a physical human-robot interaction, compliant control schemes, such as impedance/admittance control or basic gravity compensation, are essential. These control strategies significantly impact the quality of captured data. To enhance this process, prior works have explored impedance and admittance control, leveraging partial task knowledge [11], iterative physical demonstrations [12], [13], and related concepts such as progressive automation [14] and incremental learning [15].

Human-centric environments are often unstructured, cluttered and heavily dynamic, which makes learning through only a single means difficult and some times impossible, in terms of skill transferability. Furthermore, learning among human beings rarely involves a single communication channel. On the contrary, human-human learning is multi-modal, e.g. verbal/linguistic, visual (through demonstration), kinesthetic (for basic skills) etc, which is shown to be beneficial

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for the learning process [16]. Some attempts to tackle the problem of multi-modal LbD in robotics literature involve high level robot programming through a composition of basic actions [17], the combination of cameras and wearable sensors [2], refinement of kinesthetic teaching through post-training visualizations [18] or combining kinesthetic with simulations [19]. To the best of the authors' knowledge, the exploitation of visual data from depthless cameras for enhancing the kinesthetic teaching of a task has not previously been studied, in the context of LbD.

In this work, we propose an LbD method that combines the advantages of both visual and kinesthetic teaching, offering the intuitiveness and effortlessness of learning through observation while benefiting from the accuracy of kinesthetic teaching. Our approach involves a two-stage scheme that leverages visual data from a single demonstration, captured by a depthless camera, to assist the human-teacher in kinesthetic task instruction. The proposed method assumes access to an algorithm for detecting the human-hand configuration from RGB images (without depth or camera distance information), and does not require knowledge of the camera's location relative to an inertial frame.

II. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION AND CONCEPT SOLUTION

Consider the availability of a visual observation of a manual “post-grasp” task performed by a human, i.e. a video of a human hand executing a specific task. A “post-grasp task” here refers to hand movements after grasping an object, such as detaching a fruit from a branch. Let us adopt the reasonable assumption that depth information is either altogether absent from the visual observation data (i.e. an RGB camera was utilized for the frame capture), or is characterized by a relatively high uncertainty. The position and the orientation of the camera with respect to the scene is not considered to be known a priori. Let $\mathbf{x} \triangleq [\mathbf{p}^\top \mathbf{Q}^\top]^\top \in \mathcal{T}$, be the actual generalized pose of the human hand, e.g. of the wrist, where $\mathbf{p}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and $\mathbf{Q}(t) \in \mathbb{S}^3$ are the position (in Cartesian coordinates form) and orientation (in unit quaternion form) of the hand respectively, with $\mathcal{T} \triangleq \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{S}^3$ representing the generalized pose space of the hand and $\mathbb{S}^n \triangleq \{\mathbf{a} \in \mathbb{R}^{n+1} : \|\mathbf{a}\|=1\}$ the set of unit vectors (unit sphere). We further assume access to an algorithm that can estimate the human hand's position and orientation relative to the camera, e.g. MediaPipe Hands [20] or OpenPose [21]. Let $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_h(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_h(t) \in \mathbb{S}^3$ respectively denote the algorithm-estimated position (in pixel space) and orientation of the hand relative to the camera frame $\{C\}$ during the video, where $t \in [0, T]$, with $T \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ representing the demonstration duration. Figure 1 depicts the uncertainty involved in the estimated pose of the human hand.

Our aim is to exploit the initial available information captured by the camera, i.e. $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_h(t)$, $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_h(t)$, by accounting for their anisotropic uncertainty, in order to encode the skill and subsequently transfer it to the robot. To this end, we propose the augmentation of the visually perceived motion through kinesthetic means, i.e. through physical human-robot interaction, during the autonomous execution of the task by

Fig. 1: Uncertainty involved in visual observation.

the robot. A novel aspect of our approach, introduced to ensure that this augmentation is user-intuitive as well as efficient, involves using the uncertainty of the visual data to render anisotropic compliance characteristics to the robot's admittance control, i.e. relatively large kinesthetic corrections are allowed only along the directions in which the uncertainty of the initially perceived motion is relatively high.

III. PROPOSED METHOD

A. LbD through visual observation

Consider an algorithm able of identifying the 21 anatomical key-points of the human hand, i.e. four for each finger and one at the wrist, as shown in the upper part of Fig. 2. We define the hand pose based on key-points \mathbf{p}_a , \mathbf{p}_b , \mathbf{p}_c , $\mathbf{p}_d \in \mathbb{R}^3$, with \mathbf{p}_a , \mathbf{p}_c , \mathbf{p}_d representing the three vertices of the palm triangle, and \mathbf{p}_b being the base of the thumb, as depicted in Fig. 2. Notice that all three coordinates of those points are considered to be estimated (as they belong to \mathbb{R}^3), which is commonly the case for detection algorithms such as the MediaPipe algorithm; however, the z -coordinate of \mathbf{p}_a (wrist) is always zero, as it is the base key-point and therefore it is considered by definition to lie on the camera projection plane. The estimated position of the human hand is considered to be represented by the wrist and therefore $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_h \triangleq \mathbf{p}_a$, while the estimated orientation of the human hand in a rotation matrix form is defined as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{R}}_h \triangleq [\mathbf{x}_h \mathbf{y}_h \mathbf{z}_h] \in SO(3), \quad (1)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{z}_h &\triangleq \frac{\mathbf{p}_{ab} + \mathbf{p}_{ap}}{\|\mathbf{p}_{ab} + \mathbf{p}_{ap}\|} \in \mathbb{S}^2, \\ \mathbf{x}_h &\triangleq \frac{(\mathbf{I}_3 - \mathbf{z}_h \mathbf{z}_h^\top) \mathbf{p}_{ab}}{\|(\mathbf{I}_3 - \mathbf{z}_h \mathbf{z}_h^\top) \mathbf{p}_{ab}\|} \in \mathbb{S}^2, \\ \mathbf{y}_h &\triangleq \mathbf{z}_h \times \mathbf{x}_h \in \mathbb{S}^2, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

with $\mathbf{p}_{ai} \triangleq \mathbf{p}_i - \mathbf{p}_a$, $\forall i \in \{b, c, d\}$, $\mathbf{p}_{ap} \triangleq \frac{\mathbf{p}_{ac} + \mathbf{p}_{ad}}{2}$, $\mathbf{I}_3 \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ the identity matrix and “ \times ” denoting the cross product. The calculation of the corresponding unit quaternion representation $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_h$ from $\hat{\mathbf{R}}_h$ is straightforward. The z -axis is defined to point toward the opening between the palm and thumb, the primary prehensile component of the human hand.

Further, notice the similarity of the direction of the z -axis of the human hand, with that of the robotic gripper (bottom image of Fig. 2), which facilitates motion mapping for human-to-robot skill transferability.

Fig. 2: Visual detection of the pose of the human hand and the frames of the hand and robotic gripper considered.

Based on the recorded observation during a complete demonstration, i.e. $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_h(t), \hat{\mathbf{Q}}_h(t), t \in [0, T]$, we employ the Dynamic Movement Primitives (DMP) model [22] to encode the spatial and temporal characteristics of the motion. This particular choice has the benefit of single-shot model training. For the orientation part, the method proposed in [23] is utilized, which takes advantage of logarithmic mapping. The DMP model in the task-space, involves the motion generation through the on-line solution of a dynamical system, which can be expressed as follows:

$$\tau \dot{\mathbf{x}}_d = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_d; \mathbf{W}), \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_d \triangleq [\mathbf{p}_d^\top \mathbf{Q}_d^\top \dot{\mathbf{p}}_d^\top \boldsymbol{\omega}_d^\top z]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{14}$ is the state of the model (motion generation mechanism), with $\mathbf{p}_d \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{Q}_d \in \mathbb{S}^3$ being the generated reference position and unit quaternion respectively, $\boldsymbol{\omega}_d \in \mathbb{R}^3$ the generated angular velocity reference, and $z \in \mathbb{R}$ the so-called phase variable that serves as a replacement of time (one can refer to [22] for more details). Moreover, $\mathbf{f}(\cdot) : \mathbb{R}^{14} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{14}$ is the nonlinear function that maps the states to their derivatives, $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times N}$ the tunable parameters that essentially encode the motion, with $N \in \mathbb{N}$ being their number, while $\tau \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ is the time scaling parameter, through which the speed and duration of motion can be adjusted; $\tau > 1$ induces a motion with lower speed than the one demonstrated, while $\tau < 1$ induces a faster motion. Given the demonstrated motion, there are many different options to compute the \mathbf{W} values so that the generated motion (i.e. the evolution of the dynamical system) optimally mimics the demonstrated data set. The most common methods for calculating the optimal parameters \mathbf{W} are the Least Squares and the Locally Weighted Regression [22].

Remark 1. We emphasize that the estimated position and orientation of the human hand is recorded with respect to the initial identified frame of the human hand, $\{U\}$, detected by the camera at $t = 0$. Hence, the entire motion is encoded with respect to the initial grasp pose of the hand. Furthermore, given that the motion is encoded without accounting for depth information, the units of $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_h$ are not specific, but they are actually on the pixel space of the camera. However, due to the inherent spatial scaling properties of DMPs, simply defining the initial and target pose aptly adjusts the motion to be executed to the task needs, thereby compensating for this unit inconsistency of the training dataset.

B. Kinesthetic corrections

Following the initial stage, where a DMP is trained using visual data (as detailed in Subsection III-A), we propose a second stage in which the robot autonomously executes the motion with the ability, however, to introduce compliance when deemed necessary by the human user to allow for kinesthetic corrections. To further assist the user and reduce cognitive and physical effort, the compliance is enhanced along the axis with the highest current model uncertainty, as estimated based on the uncertainty in the camera's viewpoint during the visual demonstration.

To provide the system with compliant characteristics, we employ the notion of admittance control. Therefore, a target impedance model in the task-space of the robot is defined for the robot's end-effector, as follows:

$$\mathbf{M}\dot{\boldsymbol{\delta}}_v + \mathbf{D}\boldsymbol{\delta}_v + \mathbf{K}\mathbf{e} = \mathbf{F}_x, \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{M}, \mathbf{D}, \mathbf{K} \in S_{++}^6$ are the target 6D task-space positive definite inertia, damping and stiffness matrices respectively, $\boldsymbol{\delta}_v \in \mathbb{R}^6$ represents the desired deviation from the reference velocity induced by the admittance model, while $\mathbf{F}_x \triangleq [\mathbf{f}^\top \boldsymbol{\tau}^\top]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^6$ is the generalized force measurement at the end-effector with $\mathbf{f}, \boldsymbol{\tau} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ being the force and torque applied by the user to the end-effector, with S_{++}^n denoting the set of positive definite matrices. Moreover,

$$\mathbf{e} \triangleq [(\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_d)^\top \log(\mathbf{Q} * \mathbf{Q}_d^{-1})^\top]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^6, \quad (5)$$

is the error between the robot's pose, denoted with $\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{Q} \in \mathbb{S}^3$, and the reference pose generated by the visually trained DMP. Here, $\log(\cdot) : \mathbb{S}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$ is the quaternion logarithmic mapping, “*” represents the quaternion product, and $\mathbf{Q}_d^{-1} \in \mathbb{S}^3$ the quaternion inverse of \mathbf{Q}_d (more details on quaternion algebra can be found in [24]).

For rendering these specific compliant characteristics, the commanded joint velocities are computed by:

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{J}^\dagger \left(\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\mathbf{p}}_d \\ \boldsymbol{\omega}_d \end{bmatrix} + \boldsymbol{\delta}_v \right), \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}^m$ are the joint variables and $\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{q}) \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times m}$ the Jacobian matrix of the robot, with m being the number of joints and “ \dagger ” symbolizing any pseudo inverse matrix, e.g. the inverse if $m = 6$.

Based on (4), the selection of the impedance model parameters plays a crucial role on the directions in which the user

is guided during the interaction with the robot. Specifically, the reactive force experienced by the user along a specific direction is proportional to the values of the corresponding elements of matrices \mathbf{M} , \mathbf{D} and \mathbf{K} . Our aim is to append low impedance along the directions with high uncertainty.

As described in Section II, the estimated hand pose by the camera includes a measurement error, which is considered to be a random variable having a normal distribution: $\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}_6, \boldsymbol{\Sigma})$, with $\boldsymbol{\Sigma} \in S_{++}^6$ being the variance-covariance matrix of its uncertainty. Notice that, as mentioned in Remark 1, the measurement error is defined with respect to the initial pose of the human hand, as detected by the camera, i.e. with respect to $\{U\}$. In practical applications, as $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$ is generally unknown, one can use an estimate of the uncertainty. More specifically, given the the initial robot’s end-effector pose at the start of the kinesthetic correction phase, denoted as $\mathbf{R}_0 \in SO(3)$, the uncertainty with respect to the robot’s base frame is calculated as follows:

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma} \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_p & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_o \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{A} \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_c \mathbf{A}^\top, \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{A} \triangleq \mathbf{R}_0 \mathbf{R}_{cu}^\top \otimes \mathbf{I}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^6$ with $\mathbf{R}_{cu} \in SO(3)$ being the rotation matrix of frame $\{U\}$ (initially identified pose of the human hand) with respect to the camera frame and “ \otimes ” representing the Kronecker product, while $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_c \in S_{++}^6$ represents the block-diagonal (for decoupled position and orientation) uncertainty of the camera with respect to its own frame. In such a case, for an RGB camera (or for a low-depth-resolution RGB-D camera), we could consider $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_c = \text{diag}(\underline{\sigma}, \underline{\sigma}, \underline{\sigma}, \bar{\varsigma}, \bar{\varsigma}, \underline{\varsigma})^2$ with $\underline{\sigma}, \bar{\sigma}, \underline{\varsigma}, \bar{\varsigma} \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ and $\underline{\sigma} \ll \bar{\sigma}, \underline{\varsigma} \ll \bar{\varsigma}$, as the estimation involves low uncertainty only along the pixel space direction (x, y of the camera) and the rotation around its z -axis. Notice that the units of $\underline{\sigma}, \bar{\sigma}$ are “meters” and those of $\underline{\varsigma}, \bar{\varsigma}$ are “radians”. Hence, the expected deviations can be estimated on the basis of rough estimates for the motion’s range.

Under the aforementioned rationale, and given the uncertainty involved in the DMP model after the initial stage (i.e. visual training), we propose the utilization of the following anisotropic stiffness matrix:

$$\mathbf{K} \triangleq \text{diag} \left(\frac{k_p}{\lambda_{pM}} \mathbf{I}_3, \frac{k_o}{\lambda_{oM}} \mathbf{I}_3 \right) \boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{-1}, \quad (8)$$

where $\lambda_{pM}, \lambda_{oM} \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ respectively denote the maximum eigenvalues of $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_p^{-1}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_o^{-1}$, while $k_p, k_o \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ represent the selected stiffness value on the major axis of \mathbf{K} for position and orientation, respectively.

At the end of the kinesthetic correction stage, the recorded refined motion of the end-effector, i.e. $\mathbf{p}(t), \mathbf{Q}(t), \forall t \in [0, T]$, is used to retrain the DMP model.

Remark 2. *The learning process could possibly include additional kinesthetic correction iterations, which are expected to enhance the task learning.*

The overall multi-modal training scheme has been implemented in Python, utilizing the MediaPipe algorithm [20],

and is publicly available¹.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

The proposed scheme of multi-modal LbD was experimentally evaluated considering the scenario shown in Fig. 3. The task involves moving a tool along a circular path (approximately 1.5 turns) around an axis, to which the tool is connected via a thread. The task duration is $T \approx 10.5$ s. A plain RGB webcam (*Creative Live! Cam*) is used to capture data for visual training, in 30 fps. The image captured by the camera is shown in Fig. 4. Note that, given the viewpoint of the camera, the motion trajectory is ellipsoidal when projected to the camera’s visual plane.

The robotic agent is a *Universal Robots UR10e* manipulator, equipped with a custom gripper, as shown in the bottom image of Fig. 2. The gripper features three 3d-printed fingers made from a flexible material (thermoplastic polyurethane, TPU), which are actuated by a single motor. This design enables safe and adaptive grasping of various objects, as the flexible fingers conform to the shape of the object being grasped. In addition, a custom dual-handle attachment, mounted between the robot’s tool flange and the gripper, facilitates hand guidance of the robot during kinesthetic training. This is employed either for a) single-modal training using the robot’s in-built “teach mode” function, or b) the correction stage of the proposed multi-modal scheme, implemented through the anisotropic admittance controller (4). For the latter, a pushbutton, integrated in one of the handles, is used to allow user intervention by engaging the kinesthetic correction mode during execution of the visually learned motion. The force measurement required in (4) is provided by the in-build 6d force/torque sensor of UR10e, after compensating for the gripper’s gravity and applying a dead-zone filter of 4 N for the force and 0.5 Nm for torque.

The parameters of the multi-modal training scheme were specified as $\mathbf{M} = \text{diag}(10\mathbf{I}_3, 0.1\mathbf{I}_3)$, $\mathbf{D} = \text{diag}(40\mathbf{I}_3, 1.5\mathbf{I}_3)$, $k_p = 200$ N/m, $k_o = 80$ Nm/rad, $\underline{\sigma} = 10^{-3}$ m, $\bar{\sigma} = 10^3$ m, $\underline{\varsigma} = \pi/20$ rad, $\bar{\varsigma} = \pi$ rad. The DMP model uses 20 kernels. We note that the minor axis of \mathbf{K}_p is towards the y -axis with an eigenvalue that approaches zero, which means that corrections are freely facilitated along the y -axis in translation. For \mathbf{K}_o , the minor axis is towards the $x-z$ plane, with corresponding eigenvalues equal to 0.2 Nm/rad (as opposed to 80 Nm/rad exhibited along the other axis), facilitating corrections towards these directions for orientation.

For evaluating the proposed method, we compare it against a) skill learning based solely on the initial visual data, and b) skill learning through direct kinesthetic teaching (henceforth referred to as “kinesthetic-only”), using the “teach mode” of UR10e. In all cases, the robot starts from the same initial configuration to ensure a fair comparison.

The initial configuration during physical interaction of the human with the robot is shown in Fig. 5a. The paths of the robot’s tip followed during the proposed kinesthetic corrections method (blue line) and during single-modal

¹<https://github.com/CSRL-HMU/Multimodal-Visual-Kinesthetic-LbD>

Fig. 3: The post-grasp task considered for the experimental evaluation of the proposed method.

kinesthetic-only teaching (red line) are shown in Fig. 6a, alongside with the visually trained model (black line). It can be observed that due to the lack of depth information in the RGB video, the visually trained motion remains essentially planar and takes on an ellipsoidal shape. The trajectory of the kinesthetic-only training exhibits considerable oscillations, resulting from the fact that the human experiences the dynamics of the system. It should also be noted that, in this case, the user was unable to complete the demonstration within the nominal task duration of 10.5 s, with the motion ending approximately a quarter-circle early. This reflects the high cognitive load imposed on the user while attempting to compensate for the robot’s dynamics.

The initial configuration of the robot during the autonomous task execution, after the DMP encoding of the training data, is shown in Fig. 5b. Figure 6b depicts the paths followed by the tip of the robot during execution of the task. In this case, the DMP-generated reference tip trajectory ($\mathbf{p}_d, \dot{\mathbf{p}}_d, \ddot{\mathbf{p}}_d$) is tracked using the Closed Loop Inverse Kinematics (CLIK) algorithm, without accounting for the external forces exerted on the tool. Notice, in Fig. 6b, the absence of erroneous oscillations in the kinesthetic-only case, due to the filtering induced by the Gaussian function approximation of the DMP. Here, in order to assess the task performance, we estimate the radius of curvature of the path, denoted with $\hat{r}(t) \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$, in each case, at 100 equally distributed time instances within the duration of each motion², based on the following formula [25]:

$$\hat{r}(t) = \frac{\|\dot{\mathbf{p}}_d\|^3}{\sqrt{\|\dot{\mathbf{p}}_d\|^2 \|\ddot{\mathbf{p}}_d\|^2 - (\dot{\mathbf{p}}_d^\top \ddot{\mathbf{p}}_d)^2}},$$

and we compare it with the reference radius (i.e. the thread’s length), which is $r \approx 0.225$ m. The box-plots in Fig. 7 show the statistical distributions of the thus estimated radius of curvature for each case. It can be seen that the proposed method yields a learned motion that is notably closer to the reference task—at least in terms of this specific performance metric—compared to the single-modal approaches. Due to its ellipsoidal shape, the visually trained motion exhibits relatively high curvature. In contrast, the curvature of the motion trained through kinesthetic-only teaching is evidently lower than the reference, as the aforementioned

²Radius of curvature cannot be estimated when the robot is static, due to $\dot{\mathbf{p}}_d, \ddot{\mathbf{p}}_d$ being close to zero.

DMP-induced filtering is insufficient to fully correct the motion.

Fig. 4: Snapshots of the visual teaching stage, acquired by the webcam during the task demonstration.

Fig. 5: Kinesthetic training stage and autonomous task execution.

To compare the methods in terms of physical effort requirements, we consider the energy transferred from human to robot during hand guidance, computed using:

$$E^+ = \int_0^T \max(0, \mathbf{v}^\top \mathbf{F}) dt.$$

For the kinesthetic-only approach (without prior visual information) the transferred energy is computed as 35.01 J, whereas the kinesthetic correction stage of the multi-modal scheme requires only 4.92 J. This seven-fold improvement highlights the considerable efficiency advantage of the proposed method.

Fig. 6: Path followed by the robot's tip during (a) training, and (b) execution of the learned task. Black dashed line depicts a circle of radius equal to the thread's length (0.225 m), while the solid small linear segments indicate the tool z-axis at regular time intervals. The initial and final positions are denoted with "x" and "o" markers respectively (all initial positions coincide).

Fig. 7: Statistics of the learned path's radius of curvature in each case.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a novel method for a two-stage LbD is introduced, that combines depthless visual data with kinesthetic teaching for efficient human-to-robot skill transfer. In the core of the proposed admittance-based method lies an anisotropic stiffness matrix, which is defined based on the uncertainty of the visually perceived motion, to facilitate the human-teacher along the axis in which the system is currently less confident. The method is shown to outperform the single-modal learning, namely the training through solely visual or kinesthetic means, in terms of both skill transferability and physical load requirements. The tests consider a task involving a rhythmic circular motion around an axis.

Future work will involve detailed studies for the specification of the anisotropic stiffness parameters, as well as different use cases (e.g. fruit hand-picking or pick-and-place tasks). In addition, possible extensions to the proposed method will be explored, e.g. taking into account the uncertainty of the hand keypoints' detection algorithm, considering multiple kinesthetic correction iterations, or multi-view visual demonstrations.

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